

Psychosocial treatment for individuals with psychotic disorders

Guide for implementation and sustainable
use of DIALOG+ in healthcare systems
in Southeast Europe

Acknowledgement

This booklet has been produced within the IMPULSE project (Implementation of an Effective and Cost-Effective Intervention for Patients with Psychotic Disorders in Low and Middle Income Countries in South Eastern Europe). The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 779334. The funding was received through the “Global Alliance for Chronic Diseases (GACD) prevention and management of mental disorders” (SCI-HCO-07-2017) funding call.

Editors:

Nadja P. Maric, MD, PhD, Faculty of Medicine University of Belgrade & Institute of Mental Health, Belgrade, Serbia

Nikolina Jovanovic, MD, PhD, Queen Mary University of London, Unit for Social and Community Psychiatry – WHO Collaborating Centre for Mental Health Services Development, London, United Kingdom

Authors (alphabetical order):

Sanja Andric Petrovic, MD, PhD, Faculty of Medicine University of Belgrade & University Clinic for Psychiatry, Clinical Centre of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

Stefan Jerotic, MD, Faculty of Medicine University of Belgrade & University Clinic for Psychiatry, Clinical Centre of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

Tamara Pemovska, MSc, Queen Mary University of London, Unit for Social and Community Psychiatry – WHO Collaborating Centre for Mental Health Services Development, London, United Kingdom

Ivan Ristic, MD, Faculty of Medicine University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

Manuela Russo, PhD, Queen Mary University of London, Unit for Social and Community Psychiatry – WHO Collaborating Centre for Mental Health Services Development, London, United Kingdom

Mirjana Zebic, PhD, Faculty of Medicine University of Belgrade & University Clinic for Psychiatry, Clinical Centre of Serbia, Belgrade, Serbia

Published in October 2021

ISBN 978-1-910195-43-7

British Library Cataloguing in Publication Data

A catalogue record for this book is available from the British Library

**For people living with mental health problems and for all who
assist them in seeking help and in achieving recovery**

Foreword

The combination of care, medication and psychosocial interventions helps people affected by psychotic disorders to lead productive life and be integrated in society. This approach has been widely recommended and implemented in countries with developed economies, but most of the low and middle income countries (LMIC) are still far from this goal. The reasons for underuse of psychosocial interventions span from financial and organizational issues to insufficient data about the efficacy and safety of non-pharmacological interventions in the local context.

In 2018, the European Commission and Global Alliance for Chronic Diseases (GACD) invested 2.4 million Euros in the IMPULSE consortium (see Appendix - A3) to deliver a new research study called ‘Implementation of an effective and cost-effective intervention for patients with psychotic disorders in low and middle income countries in South Eastern Europe (IMPULSE)’. The main goal of the project is to improve treatment of individuals diagnosed with psychotic disorders in five low and middle income countries of Southeast Europe: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Kosovo* UN Resolution, Republic of North Macedonia, Montenegro, and Serbia. The project also focuses on bridging the gap between research and policy, facilitating community-based mental health care, facilitating user-led involvement, and building research capacity in the participating countries.

The partners, coordinated by the Queen Mary University of London, conducted a longitudinal trial which involved 468 patients and 81 clinicians from the region to explore effectiveness and implementation of a digital psychosocial intervention called DIALOG+ in healthcare systems of participating countries. The DIALOG+ intervention was designed specifically to improve therapeutic effectiveness of routine clinical meetings. The intervention was shown to be effective, cost saving and acceptable to patients and staff in the UK.

The IMPULSE study team has created this guide for all who work in the field of mental health care and who have been searching for methods which could improve routine patient-clinician meetings. This Guide offers essential advice on how to understand and to implement a psychosocial approach in order to protect and ameliorate mental health and psychosocial well-being of people with both non-affective and affective psychoses.

This publication has been created for clinicians (psychiatrists, psychologists, social workers, and nurses), patients and their caregivers, but also for policy makers and service commissioners and organizers. All of them will find new information which could be used to better integrate people with psychosis in society.

Foreword

List of Abbreviations

Content

1.0 Introduction	1
1.1 Psychosocial intervention - Definition and Scope	1
1.2 Unmet needs of patients in Southeast Europe - Focus on individuals with Psychosis Spectrum Disorders	3
2.0 What is DIALOG+?	6
3.0 Why use DIALOG+ for patients with psychosis	12
4.0 Patients' and clinicians' experiences of using DIALOG+	18
4.1 What are the benefits of using DIALOG+ in MH care?	18
4.2 Which patients should be offered DIALOG+ to maximise its benefits?	23
4.3 Which issues could be encountered while using DIALOG+?	24
4.4 Can the use of a tablet computer be problematic?	25
4.5 Duration of the DIALOG+ sessions	26
4.6 Are there any safety concerns or inconveniences associated with the DIALOG+?	26
5.0 Conclusion	28
APPENDIX	29
A1. Let's begin with DIALOG+	30
A2. About the IMPULSE study	33
A3. The IMPULSE consortium	34
REFERENCES	35

List of Abbreviations

CSQ-8	Client Satisfaction Questionnaire
EC	European Commission
GACD	Global Alliance for Chronic Diseases
ICD-10	International Classification of Disease, 10th revision
Kosovo*	UN resolution: All references in this text, whether the territory, institutions or population shall be understood in full compliance with the United Nations Security Council Resolution 1244
LMIC	Low and Middle income Countries
MANSA	Manchester Short Assessment of Quality of Life
MH	Mental Health
PREM	Patient Reported Experience Measures
PSD	Psychosis Spectrum Disorders
QoL	Quality of Life
RCT	Randomized Controlled Trial
SD	Standard Deviation
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SEE	Southeast Europe
TAU	Treatment as Usual
WHO	World Health Organization

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Psychosocial intervention - definition and scope

The biopsychosocial model that forms the foundation of modern psychiatry posits that the occurrence, course and outcome of mental disorders are determined by complex and dynamic interactions between biological, psychological and social factors. Accordingly, the majority of professional guidelines recommend combined application of biological and psychosocial interventions and individualized treatment plans (NICE, 2014).

The psychosocial interventions for mental health (MH) and substance use disorders consist of **“interpersonal or informational activities, techniques, or strategies that target biological, behavioural, cognitive, emotional, social, or environmental factors with the aim of improving health functioning and well-being”** (England et al, 2015). This term encompasses a broad range of interventions with different theoretical foundations - psychotherapies, community-based treatment, vocational rehabilitation, peer support services, etc. Their primary goal is to ameliorate the treatment of MH conditions through improvement of symptoms, quality of life (QoL), psychological and social functioning (Dua et al, 2011; Bajaj Janovic et al, 2020). In general, studies comparing effectiveness of different types of psychosocial interventions do not give preference to any of these methods, further suggesting that their successful application is primarily determined by the quality of the achieved patient-clinician therapeutic relationship.

There is evidence that shared decision-making results in a better patient-clinician relationship and better outcomes in mental health settings (Maj et al, 2021).

Efficacy of psychosocial interventions in the treatment of mental disorders is evident when administered in combination with pharmacotherapy or even on their own (Barth et al, 2013; Cuijpers et al, 2008, 2013, 2014; Institute of Medicine (US) Committee on Crossing the Quality Chasm: Adaptation to Mental Health and Addictive Disorders, 2006). Interestingly, both clinicians and patients (especially younger patients and women) prefer them to medications for treatment of MH conditions in situations when these two approaches are shown to have comparable efficacy (McHugh et al, 2013).

However, psychosocial interventions are not considered to be an alternative to pharmacotherapy. Rather, this is an integrative part of the holistic treatment approach, pivotal for successful treatment outcomes for various mental disorders. **For certain vulnerable groups of patients for whom pharmacologic treatment is not recommended** (i.e. child-bearing women, very young children, individuals with complex medical conditions), **psychosocial interventions might be the only therapeutic option** (Committee on Developing Evidence-Based Standards for Psychosocial Interventions for Mental Disorders, 2015).

How and why psychosocial interventions lead to change?

The link between MH and psychosocial factors is reciprocal and reversible. As adverse life events and emotional trauma are well known to have a significant role in the development of mental disorders, so the favourable psychosocial circumstances, such as effective psychosocial interventions, can also have a significant positive effect on MH and wellbeing. The human brain is adaptable to external stimuli through the life-course. Anything that contributes to the reduction in risk factors causing mental distress as well as the increase in protective factors, promotes positive MH as an individual and public good.

The assessment and management of persons with psychosis cannot be simply presented through a guideline. It is an iterative process of “finding it out together”, requiring (Maj et al, 2021):

- A solid therapeutic relationship characterized by genuine interest and curiosity
- A caring attitude
- The ability to project trust and stimulate motivation

1.2 Unmet needs of patients in Southeast Europe - focus on individuals with psychosis spectrum disorders

Severe mental disorders such as psychosis spectrum disorders – PSD (schizophrenia spectrum disorders, schizo-affective disorder, bipolar disorder and unipolar depression with psychotic features) represent a major health, social, and economic burden for patients, families, caregivers, and the wider society. Primary psychoses are highly burdensome worldwide and almost 3/4ths of the global burden is concentrated in LMICs (Charlson et al, 2018).

During the past 25-30 years LMICs in Southeast Europe (SEE) underwent major socio-political changes such as transition from socialist to full market economies, a decade of war and armed conflict, a hardening of social divisions along ethnic and religious lines, exacerbated processes of social exclusion, financial crises, and decreased capacity of state systems to care for the most vulnerable in society. Outpatient psychiatric services in SEE have been mostly limited to the prescription of medications (Winkler et al, 2017).

Healthcare systems in high income countries recommend and provide a combination of care, medication and psychosocial interventions which successfully helps people affected by psychotic disorders to lead a productive life and be integrated in society. Although these interventions could not be always validated by research (Maj et al, 2021) and some of them have been criticized to be stereotyped (i.e. not adapted to the characteristics and needs of the individual patient in the specific stage of his/her illness), they have been available to most of the community treated patients in high income countries.

A significant lack of psychiatrists and MH nurses in comparison to well-developed European countries can be one of the major limitations for providing a comprehensive treatment of MH outpatients in LMICs (WHO, 2014, 2017; Maric et al, 2019). Another shortcoming could be the underuse of interventions which would allow for a systematic patient–clinician interaction in community MH settings. In LMICs less funding and less qualified staff is available to provide structured non-pharmacological interventions. According to the most recent World Health Organization Atlas – country profiles (WHO, 2017), the number of psychiatrists in the LMIC countries in SEE is relatively low comparing to the developed European countries (e.g. France, Germany, Slovenia) which consistently have more human resources allocated to MH care (Table 1.1).

**Table 1.1 Mental health workforce - country profiles
(rate per 100 000 population; WHO 2017)**

Country	Psychiatrists	Psychologists	MH nurses
Bosnia and Herzegovina	8.0	1.5	22.1
France	20.9	48.7	98.0
Germany	13.2	48.6	Not reported
Montenegro	8.3	Not reported	18.3
Republic of North Macedonia	14.4	2.4	Not reported
Serbia	8.6	4.6	13.2
Slovenia	12.0	9.7	36.7

The lack of resources affects outpatient psychiatric care in different ways (e.g. appointment duration, type of care, etc.) and limits comprehensive treatment of a large proportion of MH outpatients. PSD patients have limited access to outpatient psychiatric care due to barriers that are not well understood yet.

Discrimination and social isolation due to stigma increase loneliness and feeling of helplessness. Such state of complete or near-complete lack of contact between an individual and society might lead to a way of life in which visiting the grocery store may be the only social event of the day for many persons with schizophrenia or other primary psychoses. Such an outcome is an individual and collective tragedy, knowing that social contacts are metaphorically the breath of life.

Currently, patients with the same MH issues can receive different care depending on the clinician, region or country. A review of health practices and MH policies of SEE countries (Jovanovic et al, 2020; Stevovic et al, 2021) showed that:

1. Patients with PSD are mainly treated in hospital-based settings
2. In hospital-based outpatient services, patients are primarily seen by psychiatrists, every 1-3 months, and the duration of routine meetings is 15-30 minutes
3. The meetings mainly focus on review of medication
4. Provision of psychosocial interventions is not structured
5. Community-based MH services are still rare

Millions of MH patients are offered routine meetings with MH professionals worldwide and in fact, these meetings can be seen as a cornerstone of community MH care. The question is how to make them therapeutic and meaningful for both patients and clinicians. DIALOG+ is one such intervention designed to make routine clinical meetings therapeutically effective (Priebe & McCabe, 2006). Please find more information about DIALOG+ in the next section.

2.0 What is DIALOG+?

DIALOG+ is a digital psychosocial intervention which makes routine clinical meetings between patients with psychosis and clinicians more productive, with the aim to **improve MH care** (Priebe et al, 2013). The intervention makes conversation between the patient and the clinician more structured and comprehensive by covering different aspects of life and MH care. At the beginning of each clinical encounter the patient is invited to rate his/hers satisfaction with different life aspects. Next, the patient is asked to identify issues he/she wants to work on whereupon a specific approach is applied to find solutions to identified problems. Sessions last up to 30 minutes and can be delivered every month or every couple of months.

The intervention is manualised and supported by a freely available app (Priebe et al, 2020). The development of this intervention was based on studies that showed how structured communication between the patient and the clinician in the community improves QoL, need for care and treatment outcomes (DIALOG; Priebe et al, 2007). After these initial findings, the development of a structured psychosocial intervention moved towards including aspects of **solution-focused therapy**, which resulted in the DIALOG+ intervention (Priebe et al, 2013).

Key features

The basic principles of the DIALOG+ intervention (see Figure 2.1) are:

1 Collaborative clinician-patient approach

- rejecting the old-notions of asymmetrical, paternalistic relationship between the clinician and the patient, strengthening the therapeutic alliance, mutual understanding and shared decision-making lead to improvements of QoL during the DIALOG+ sessions.

2 Patient-centred communication

- patient selects domains of life that he/she wants to discuss in greater detail and all further discussion on the selected topics is done at the pace of the patient.

3 Holistic care planning

- DIALOG+ provides a comprehensive screening of mental, physical and social problems, leads to plans for actions in all these areas, and reduces an inefficient fragmentation of care planning.

4 Structured assessment

- DIALOG+ enables routine screening for difficulties in the patient's life that may not be overtly apparent.

5 Solution - focused process - instead of extensively focusing on problems, the focus is moved towards constructing possible solutions. The whole 4-step approach helps patients understand their situation, look forward to desired alternatives, explore their options, and agree on actions that are to be taken.

6 Technology-assisted process - a tablet computer facilitates the process of DIALOG+ intervention. It can be used collaboratively or only by the clinician, as per patient preference.

7 Monitoring of patient progress and service evaluation - the use of tablet computer makes it easy to keep all of the patient ratings and agreed actions recorded (all data are available in electronic form), enables comparisons between different sessions and tracking the progress easily.

8 Data safety - all of the recorded information are password protected.

Figure 2.1 Key components of DIALOG+, including mechanisms of action, and main outcomes that result from the use of DIALOG+ (Jovanovic et al, 2020).

DIALOG+ takes the clinician and the patient through a structured, step-by-step approach, addressing key areas of the patient's life.

1. The first phase is **assessment of the patient satisfaction with:**

Eight life domains

- mental health
- physical health
- job situation
- accommodation
- leisure activities
- relationship with partner/family
- friendships
- personal safety

Three treatment aspects:

- medication
- practical help
- meetings with clinician

2. The second phase includes advancing through a **solution-focused process targeted at the selected life domain. This solution-focused process is divided into four steps:**

- a) Understanding
- b) Looking forward
- c) Exploring options
- d) Agreeing on specific actions

The described step-by-step procedure is summarized in the Appendix (A1) and detailed description of these concepts is included in the DIALOG+ manual.

Monitoring of patient progress and service evaluation

So far, attempts to establish outcome assessment in routine community MH care have largely failed (Kilbourne et al, 2018), partly because it is difficult to motivate clinicians and patients to rate and enter outcome data on a regular basis. DIALOG+ provides a method to generate such data in a way that is meaningful to clinicians and patients, and is likely to facilitate routine outcome assessment. The ratings generated in DIALOG+ have been shown to be psychometrically sound.

The DIALOG satisfaction scale contains 11 questions where patients rate their satisfaction with eight life domains and three treatment aspects on a 7-point scale (from 1='totally dissatisfied' to 7='totally satisfied'). Every single item is meaningful and can be interpreted on its own, and the scale also provides the scores for subjective QoL and for treatment satisfaction. The scale has been shown to have good psychometric properties and is widely used in both routine care and research in the UK. It can be used for the purposes of treatment and service evaluation based on patient-reported outcomes.

On the service level, DIALOG+ brings an opportunity for implementation monitoring based on two types of activities: process monitoring and outcome monitoring. In terms of process, the question arises whether and how interventions are carried out, and in terms of outcomes, whether interventions produce the desired effect. The success of monitoring depends directly on the defined indicators. Indicators should be objective, measurable and precise markers of progress. During monitoring, the so-called process indicators should indicate the scope, efficiency and quality of implemented activities, i.e. whether and how something was done. Since DIALOG+ provides planning, assessment, intervention and evaluation in one procedure, it can automatically deliver patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs, subjective quality of life) and patient-reported experience measures (PREMs, treatment satisfaction).

Regarding monitoring of outcomes, it is important to monitor their sustainability, and for this purpose it is recommended to measure the achieved outcomes over 6-12 months after the end of the intervention. Regarding the outcome, it is necessary to identify the costs - track the number of sessions, average duration of sessions, the number of visits to the doctor and estimate the costs with appropriate measuring instruments.

3.0 Why use DIALOG+ for patients with psychosis?

- DIALOG+ equips both the clinician and the patient with a structured method to explore and deal with problems during routine clinical meetings
- IMPULSE study found DIALOG+ to be effective and acceptable for patients and clinicians in SEE (see Appendix 1)
- The DIALOG+ App and supporting manual are available in >15 languages and are all free to download
- Operational guide, background information and publications about DIALOG+ are freely available (<https://dialog.elft.nhs.uk>)

Research from the UK (2017)

The research study conducted in the UK (Priebe et al. 2015) showed that DIALOG+ promoted better MH (reduced psychiatric symptoms), improved QoL, reduced unmet needs and influenced better objective social outcomes for patients with PSD.

The intervention's effectiveness was shown to be comparable to results from studies on cognitive behavior therapy's effectiveness for people with PSD (the overall effect size was around 0.3).

The intervention has been considered cost-effective, as it improved outcomes and saved costs (Priebe et al, 2017).

Research from SEE (2021)¹

Considering the previously established effectiveness and cost effectiveness in the UK, the IMPULSE study aimed to evaluate the usefulness of DIALOG+ in a different, local context of Southeast European LMICs over a 12-month-period (see Appendix 2).

What are the main findings of the study?

DIALOG+ is not difficult to adhere to

All clinicians remained in the study until its end and they tended to adhere to the DIALOG+ manual when delivering the intervention. Variations can be seen in two elements at the beginning of the intervention such as initial reviewing of domains and selecting at least three for further discussion.

There were no significant differences in dropout rates between the DIALOG+ and treatment as usual (TAU) groups. None of the patients dropped out from causes related to intervention or research methods.

Delivery of DIALOG+ is feasible

The DIALOG+ intervention is feasible and acceptable for patients with psychosis and clinicians working in MH services. Patients with psychosis are happy to attend sessions with DIALOG+ and they engage well with the intervention.

DIALOG+ is effective

The DIALOG+ intervention has been shown to significantly improve patients' QoL as measured by the Manchester Short Assessment of Quality of Life - MANSAs (Priebe et al, 1999). The QoL improvements are seen after four monthly sessions (Figure 3.1).

¹For more information on the results in this and the subsequent pages see Jovanovic et al, 2021 and Pemovska et al, 2021.

Figure 3.1 Differences in Quality of Life after 4 DIALOG+ sessions

Focusing on the Serbian sample, where six DIALOG+ sessions were delivered during the 12-months period and without interruption by the pandemic circumstances, an average score of QoL was higher in the DIALOG+ group compared to TAU (Figure 3.2). At the moment, this is the longest observation of DIALOG+ use and efficacy (in comparison to TAU) in out patients with severe mental disorders in SEE.

Figure 3.2 Differences in Quality of life on the Serbian sample*

*The IMPULSE RCT began before the COVID-19 pandemic (February 2019), however, only the participants from Serbia completed all 6 sessions planned before the pandemic started in March 2020. In all other sites, the number of visits not affected by the pandemic was four or five out of six. Thus, the 12-month results are presented only for the Serbian site were unaffected by the possible influence of the pandemic on QoL of the participants.

What is MANSA?

Modern MH services not only aim to help patients control their symptoms, but also to help them manage everyday life and to live as good lives as possible.

QoL is increasingly included as an outcome measure in MH research, based on definition as “adequate resources, fulfilment of social roles in multiple life domains, satisfaction with life in various domains, and general life satisfaction” (Lehman, 1988).

The MANSA is a brief and easily applicable scale (Priebe et al, 1999). The instrument applies a generic concept of QoL, assessing patient satisfaction with many aspects of life: life in general, employment, financial situation, friendships, daily activities, accommodation, personal safety, fellow residents, sex life, relationships with family, physical and mental health. Satisfaction is rated on 7-point rating scales, ranging from 1 (‘could not be worse’) to 7 (‘could not be better’), with 4 (‘alternately satisfied and dissatisfied’) as a midpoint.

Mean MANSA score of 4.8 (SD = 0.9) was found for the Balkan general population sample (more than 3300 Balkan residents were assessed in 2005-6), and around 4.0 (SD = 0.9) in a sample of first episode psychosis patients from Europe (Fleischhacker et al, 2005).

DIALOG+ is safe to use

DIALOG+ use was not associated with negative events or side effects over the period of 12 months.

DIALOG+ prolongs duration of routine meetings by 8 minutes on average

When the intervention is offered within routine clinical appointments, duration of an appointment is on average 28 minutes. Comparatively, routine clinical appointments without the DIALOG+ intervention last 20 minutes on average (Figure 3.3). This indicates that the intervention prolongs the duration of appointments by 8 minutes. Nevertheless, the duration is still under 30 minutes which is a norm for routine outpatient appointments in most countries.

Figure 3.3 Average duration of sessions in the TAU and DIALOG+ throughout the trial

DIALOG+ pays off in the long term

The average costs of delivering DIALOG+ intervention in SEE countries was €129.32 per participant over the 12-month trial period. The intervention has been shown to save costs for some healthcare systems (e.g. in Serbia and North Macedonia) (Feng et al, 2021).

DIALOG+ is a comprehensive intervention

DIALOG+ enables an assessment of all areas of a patient’s wellbeing. In practice we saw that all 11 domains were at one point or another chosen to be discussed by the patient - suggesting that patients need and are willing to discuss all of these areas of their life and DIALOG+ meets that need. In the vast majority of sessions at least one action was determined. The most commonly discussed life domains were Mental Health, Partner/Family and Leisure Activities (Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.4 Frequency of selection of various life domains for each session for the group that was using DIALOG+

4.0 Patients and clinicians' experiences of using DIALOG+

The vast majority of patients and clinicians who used the DIALOG+ intervention have found it acceptable and useful (Pemovska et al, 2021). After the IMPULSE clinical trial ended, patients and clinicians were asked to share their views on using the intervention in MH care. This section highlights perceived gains of the intervention, the type of patients who should be offered DIALOG+ to maximize its benefits, and how to address technical and other issues.

4.1 What are the benefits of using DIALOG+ in MH care?²

The majority of patients are able to use the intervention as intended, e.g. to select at least one area for further discussion, discuss at least one area with the 4-step approach and suggest or agree actions to improve their satisfaction. Both patients and clinicians observed many benefits for patients and positive effects of DIALOG+, such as:

- increased self-awareness,
- empowerment,
- increased productivity,
- improved relationships with family/friends and their clinician,
- improved physical and mental wellbeing,
- increased patient involvement in treatment,
- improved treatment adherence,
- decreased doses of medicines.

²For more information on the results in this and the subsequent pages see Pemovska et al, 2021.

Benefits perceived by patients

DIALOG+ sessions were enjoyable

"I enjoyed it altogether... I can really say that it was a pleasant experience."

(Patient from Serbia, male, 39 years)

"It was so good that I was surprised."

(Patient from Kosovo*, male, 48 years)

Patients felt empowered, important and appreciated, their voice was heard and their needs were addressed

"I felt really good, just kind of ... I don't know how to explain ... I felt like I was important and that everything I say really matters."

(Patient from Bosnia and Herzegovina, male, 34 years)

"I have felt as though I was with a partner [regarding the clinician]. We worked and communicated as though being called to work together."

(Patient from Kosovo*, male, 44 years)

The intervention was preferred compared to existing routine psychiatric appointments

"So, in these DIALOG+ meetings, you simply have advice on what and how to do, to try to change something for the better, in relation to what bothers you at that moment, what axes you, what makes you nervous. And on regular check-ups, for example, these are the essential questions 'how you are, how you feel, whether there is a drop in mood, whether you may be too active or too passive, how much you like the therapy', and if I say I feel a drop in mood, a drop in activity, the doctor reacts immediately with the intensification of therapy."
(Patient from Montenegro, female, 44 years)

"[DIALOG+] is different, it's different, my doctor gave me responsibilities from the beginning... but there is no comparison how many things we have listed in DIALOG+ sessions, about what I should do or what I would do, we have not discussed my whole condition so thoroughly"
(Patient from North Macedonia, female, 32 years)

Intervention helped patients to better understand their problems

"I was able to better understand my physical and mental condition [with DIALOG+]."
(Patient from Serbia, male, 57 years)

Patients appreciated focus on solutions than to problems

"So it was very good to know that I always go home with something I need to do afterwards and that, I know for sure because I was told so, should make nice changes, so as far as that goes, it was great, I always had some assignments, something to do and have fun."

(Patient from Bosnia and Herzegovina, female, 22 years)

Patients appreciated proactive attitude and setting actions tailored to their specific needs, priorities and abilities which facilitated the implementation of actions in the patient's daily life.

"I think DIALOG+ helped me the most when it comes to getting a job...we agreed on the task of printing job adverts with phone numbers and posting them. I did that...it didn't take long and I got my first job."

(Patient from Serbia, male, 40 years)

Benefits perceived by clinicians

Improved communication skills and therapeutic relationship

"We have deepened and expanded the way we communicate... our communication was excellent... I think [patients] liked and enjoyed that special time dedicated to them... more time was devoted to them and thus the quality of communication has improved"

(Serbia, psychiatrist, female, 65 years)

Better insight into patient's overall condition

"DIALOG+ helped me to gain a greater insight into the social part of the patient's life and thus a more realistic insight into the mental state and his mental capacities."

(North Macedonia, psychiatrist, female, 48)

Improved clinical skills

"It has helped me as a mental health professional, in terms of approaching the client"
(Kosovo*, nurse, female, 41)

Increased insight into the effects of the clinician's work with patients and ability to monitor their condition over time

"In principle, it was definitely really important to me that I could follow what [patients] did, how they did it. As for me personally as a practitioner, the intervention was really helpful."

(Montenegro, psychiatrist, female, 38)

Good fit to existing clinical practice and compatible with perceived "best clinical practice":

"Well this represents modernization of psychiatric methods with evidence-based medicine, I think things like that always improve service."

(Bosnia and Herzegovina, psychiatrist, female, 49)

4-step approach and setting actions was seen as simple and useful part of the intervention

"...in three or four simple steps you can effectively formulate the instructions on what should be done - what the patient should do, what should someone from his environment do, and what the therapist should do."

(Serbia, psychiatrist, male, 43)

DIALOG+ aligned with clinicians values and what care for people with psychosis should look like

"Patients felt important, they felt that someone was taking care of them, that we are monitoring their condition from the beginning, that what they said was important."

(Bosnia and Herzegovina, social worker, female, 45)

4.2 Which patients should be offered DIALOG+ to maximise its benefits?³

The intervention is easier to deliver to more talkative patients, who are introspective, committed, open-minded to try new things and take action to change, accepting that they need help and are willing to receive it. These patients are more likely to engage and benefit more from DIALOG+. Certain **personality characteristics**, such as openness to experience and conscientiousness, are believed to positively impact the effectiveness of DIALOG+.

Clinicians felt that patients were largely able to easily participate in the DIALOG+ sessions, to recognize the steps involved in the intervention and how it works. For example, a clinician from Serbia (psychiatrist, male, 35) said:

It was pretty easy. I think it was easy for both me and them to adapt, the application is quite, let's say, internet-friendly... patients immediately figured out how to do it... the instructions from the application itself were pretty clear."

³For more information on the results in this and the subsequent pages see Pemovska et al, 2021.

4.3 Which issues could be encountered while using DIALOG+?³

The adherence to the main principles of the DIALOG+ intervention and fulfilling the agreed actions depend largely on the current illness' phase and prescribed medications. In particular, from the clinicians' perspective the presence of pronounced **cognitive impairment** or **negative symptoms** was shown to limit the likelihood of completing actions markedly.

Some patients reported that the intervention was perceived as **cognitively demanding, complex, too long and too structured** which could lead to monotony, etc. The useful recommendation, supported by the accounts from clinicians and patients that used DIALOG+ as a part of the IMPULSE study, is that **actions set should be simple and well-tailored to the patients' needs and abilities**.

Lack of patients' motivation and willingness to proactively take up the agreed actions is also considered a hindrance to completing the assigned tasks.

A patient from Bosnia (male, 45) shared:

"...but I did not always complete all of the tasks, I was simply in the phase where I could not do much."

A clinician from Bosnia (psychiatrist, female, 49) pointed out:

"Well, of course, these activities depend a lot on their current clinical condition and their mental state, and we know that it often oscillates and can be caused by... well, certain changes for the worse can be caused by some external factors, family relationships, social life... and financial problems of course... so sometimes [patients] are not motivated to work on some activities, sometimes it's their medications that slow them down..."

Patients with **hearing problems** required more time and effort and some patients needed more time to open up and talk freely.

Dealing with completing actions can sometimes be outside of the patients' control. Several external and internal factors, such as **lack of support, financial resources, motivation and poor MH** might hinder patients in the process of completing the agreed actions. Some clinicians reported that they felt disempowered to help their patients in life areas they perceived as challenging and that were not directly connected to medical treatment, such as job search or any other material resources.

³For more information on the results in this and the subsequent pages see Pemovska et al, 2021

The job search was particularly problematic due to the economic situation and limited opportunities. In this situation, clinicians were advised to discuss opportunities for volunteering or engagement with non-governmental organisations as a step towards finding employment.

4.4 Can the use of a tablet be problematic?³

A large number of clinicians and patients enrolled in the IMPULSE study perceived **tablets** as **useful** and spoke about the various features of tablets they used during DIALOG+ sessions that proved to be helpful. Overall, the tablet was perceived to be **helpful** in following and monitoring patients' condition.

A patient from Serbia (male, 47) shared:

"It is good to record on the tablet what we talked about last time, what we are talking about now, whether the situation is better or worse - in terms of assessment, evaluation and patient's general condition. So, it is useful because it records the data, it memorizes everything that was said."

Despite the usefulness of tablets, it might not be an appropriate tool to use with every patient, as not everyone is fond of technology. Some patients – particularly the elderly and/or those with more pronounced paranoid symptoms, might be **hesitant towards using the tablet**.

A clinician from North Macedonia (psychiatrist, female, 53) emphasised:

"The only problem was with the older patients who did not know how to manage tablet, but they refused my assistance to insert the scores for them. The older patients thought that it would be better if they were entering the scores themselves, or at least if we were entering together, instead of me doing this for them,"

Referring to the tablet, a clinician from Kosovo* (nurse, female, 55) mentioned that it is:

"Not for everyone. For example, not everyone liked it. But most of them do, about 80% of them liked it."

Technical issues such as tablets accidentally shutting the app down and consequently losing the data they have previously entered rarely happen. In all cases where clinicians reported difficulties experienced during the intervention delivery - they managed to resolve them successfully. This is addressed during clinicians' training and clinicians are leading on this and so patients do not need to be familiar with the use of tablet or digital technology.

³For more information on the results in this and the subsequent pages see Pemovska et al, 2021

4.5 Duration of the DIALOG sessions³

Clinicians' impression was that appointments should be kept under 30 minutes or otherwise they can be exhausting to patients. For example, a clinician from Serbia (psychiatrist, female, 45) pointed out:

"They [patients] wanted it [session] to last a little shorter... If something lasts longer than half an hour that is too much for chronic psychiatric patients. That's what we [clinicians] think, and so do they [patients]... it might be a little too extensive for one assessment."

According to a patient from Serbia (male, 40 years) longer sessions were not helpful:

"There were some sessions after which I was completely exhausted... I needed to recover after them."

As previously mentioned, the duration of DIALOG+ sessions was on average 28 minutes which was on average 8 minutes longer than the existing routine psychiatric appointments. Nevertheless, the session duration is still under 30 minutes and these extra minutes can translate into important benefits for the patients.

4.6 Are there any safety concerns or inconveniences associated with the DIALOG+?³

DIALOG+ has not been associated with any adverse events. Like in any other clinical meeting, some patients might be upset due to recalling distressing personal experiences, mental, physical health and/or social functioning problems.

Some cognitive and psychological burden can be associated with using the intervention in certain patients, as well as discomfort due to the novel way of conducting their clinical meetings. However, this should be reduced as DIALOG+ sessions progress.

³For more information on the results in this and the subsequent pages see Pemovska et al, 2021

A clinician from Serbia (psychiatrist, female, 65) said:

"Afterwards, [meetings] became more spontaneous. Like with everything that is new, at the beginning we were both tense."

It is important **to take time to familiarize patients with the intervention**, as this approach could potentially reduce the feelings of uncertainty and discomfort that patients can experience during their initial sessions.

Another clinician from Serbia (psychiatrist, female, 45) emphasised:

"It became easier over time and more comfortable. The first contacts with patients were maybe even somewhat uncomfortable for the patients because they didn't know what it was all about, what we were going to ask them, who would know about it... I mean, the patients liked to know those things... when we explained everything, then each subsequent appointment was easier because they already knew what awaited them, what the questions were and what we were going to talk about."

A patient from Bosnia (male, 34) highlighted:

"It was easier the second and the third time because I didn't know what they would ask me in the first session... I was thinking what to do if some questions were awkward and I couldn't answer them, what if something went unanswered... and so on. Later I knew what would happen in the session."

Conversely, the patients who prefer more spontaneity during their meetings with clinicians might consider DIALOG+ sessions as too rigid and slightly monotonous due to the predetermined order of their content.

A patient from North Macedonia (female, 33) shared:

"It may be better to be more like a conversation, to look less like a program, to come more naturally..."

5.0 Conclusion

The assessment and management of persons with psychosis is not linear, but rather an iterative process requiring a solid therapeutic relationship, a caring attitude, and the ability to build trust and stimulate motivation. The IMPULSE study, supported by a multi-disciplinary Consortium of experts in psychiatry, psychology, implementation science, health economy and transcultural research, conducted a mixed method, multiple case implementation study across the SEE region. It formulated a contextually appropriate approach in order to optimise and implement the delivery of DIALOG+, an evidence-based, easily deliverable, affordable and cost-saving psychosocial intervention across different healthcare systems.

The study showed that DIALOG+ provided a structured and comprehensive way to deliver routine clinical appointments. The intervention equipped both the clinician and the patient with a method to explore and deal with problems and was found effective and acceptable.

On the basis of this evidence, policymakers, planners and professional bodies in Southeast Europe, as well as in other LMICs worldwide, are called for action in relation to improving treatment of individuals with psychosis. The DIALOG+ intervention can be considered for treatment recommendations/guidelines and policies in each country.

To conclude, very few non-pharmacological interventions have been developed specifically for patients with psychosis and rigorously tested in mental health services. The DIALOG+ intervention has the potential to overcome this gap in provision of high quality care for patients with psychosis. The intervention seems to improve outcomes for patients with psychosis as well as utilisation of resources for healthcare systems. For these reasons, mental health services should consider wide implementation of DIALOG+ to achieve better clinical outcomes and save costs.

Appendix

A1. Let's begin with DIALOG+

Prerequisites (i. e. what do I need to start?)

Technical equipment and tips

- **Portable device with Android or iOS operating system** - preferably a hand-held tablet computer with a touchscreen and a minimum of 9 inch diagonal
- Temporary **access to the internet** (Wi-Fi network) in order to download the DIALOG+ application on the device
- **DIALOG+ application** - available for free on Google Play and Apple Store (the link to the application as well as an e-learning module, and other useful resources are available on: www.dialog.elft.nhs.uk)
- Upon starting the DIALOG+ App, the user will be prompted to enter his email address and **set a password**, so that any confidential information about the patient or the contents of the session is adequately protected.
- Users should make sure they **select the preferred language in the application settings**, since DIALOG+ application is translated in over 10 languages

Formal training in the application of DIALOG+ intervention

- Training is available upon request from the **IMPULSE research team**.
- **The core training** consists of **one three-hour training session** covering description of DIALOG+ background, brief description of the results of previous efficacy trials, and a detailed analysis of the 4-step approach. Attending clinicians watch the presentation and video demonstrations and afterwards practice role-play vignettes and DIALOG+ simulation using the App and tablet.
- **Top-up sessions** are furtherly scheduled, as necessary.

About a three-hour training session - clinician from Serbia:

"It was completely OK... we had that one introductory meeting and then we had a special training where we were trained how to go through the questionnaire itself, through the application ... we were in contact all the time, for any ambiguity, any problem, and everything else... So as far as cooperation is concerned, I really don't have any objections, even more, I can only say all the best."

The delivery of the DIALOG+ intervention in practice (i. e. how do I start?)

As mentioned, collaborative, **person-centred approach** is paramount in DIALOG+ sessions. The clinician should position the tablet between himself and the patient so that the patient can observe any information that is displayed on the tablet, and the whole process should be completely transparent.

Although it can be used in a variety of different settings, DIALOG+ is an intervention that was initially designed to be used in an **outpatient hospital**, or other similar professional **community MH service**. As such, DIALOG+ sessions are used in the context of a quiet room with total privacy, with a clinician-patient agreement on confidentiality, as is common in the usual outpatient MH practice. It is recommended that the clinician reserves enough time, so that the session can be adequately completed. The usual DIALOG+ session lasts about 30 minutes. First sessions could be slightly longer (up to 40-45min).

Summary of DIALOG+

Figure A1. Process of the DIALOG+ session and the 4-step approach (DIALOG+ Manual)

After logging-in, the page containing the DIALOG satisfaction scale is displayed. Patients are asked about their satisfaction with seven life domains (mental health, physical health, job situation, accommodation, leisure activities, partner/family friendships, personal safety) and three treatment aspects (medication, meetings with clinicians, practical health). **These questions have been proven as sufficient in allowing the patient to raise almost any problem or obstacle they may have in life.**

Patients are asked to rate each of the domains on a **7-point Likert scale** (1 - totally dissatisfied / 7 - totally satisfied), and after each question - “**How satisfied are you...?**” there is a prompt “**Do you need additional help in this area?**”. The patient’s answers on all of these questions are saved, and the patient and the clinician can now review these scores.

The **overview of all scores** has proven to be very useful. The patient can clearly visualise in which domains are his strengths, and weaknesses, and where their current problems are. It is recommended that the **clinician comments on the strengths** - the domains that are positively scored in the first place. An additional benefit of using the app is the **option to compare the given scores** of the patient with the scores from one of the previous sessions, which are stored in the app. Both the patient and the clinician can thus **clearly visualise the improvement or a deterioration** in the quality of specific life areas.

Afterwards, the patient selects a domain that he/she wishes to elaborate during the current session. **The maximum number of domains that can be selected for discussion is 3** as to keep the session efficient and in the constraints of an acceptable time interval. The patient and the clinician proceed to **the 4-step approach** that is predominantly based on the principles of solution-focused therapy. Three (or less) selected areas are addressed, in turn, with the 4-step approach. The four steps are then shown on the tablet. An additional benefit of using the DIALOG+ app is the fact that there is a **help button** placed on the screen next to each step. If the clinician does not remember what the step is about or wants more information, he can select this button, and get more explanations with more examples.

The **first step** is based on “**Understanding**” the problem. The clinician queries the patient on why he/she has given a specific rating on a selected life domain and what is still working in the current situation. With this approach, while trying to understand the patient’s problem, the clinician acknowledges the fact that, even though the situation could be improved, there are still some aspects of it that the patient is content with.

Example: The patient is not satisfied with his medication. He has given a score of 2 out of 7 on the “medication” treatment aspect. Why this score? The sedating side-effects are too severe, and the patient spends much of the day sleeping, or in a drowsy state. What is still working in this situation? The medication is helping him in reducing the voices that he has previously heard during the day, which added greatly to his distress.

The **second step** is called “**Looking forward**”. The clinician asks about the best case scenario for the patient looking at the long term goals accordingly. Even if they are not achievable at the moment, the patient orients himself/herself towards such goals, instead of dwelling and ruminating on problems. While keeping that in mind, the clinician should ask - what would be the smallest improvement that would make a difference in the current situation? (e.g. the smallest improvement that would move the score up by one point). The clinician and patient are thus breaking up the process of improvement into segments that are realistic and achievable, in the short term.

Example: The best case scenario would be, not taking the medication at all, not having to think about dosage regimens, or suffer side effects. While keeping this in mind as an ideal goal, the clinician and the patient discuss the smallest improvement that could be made. Patient believes that the smallest improvement in his satisfaction would be if he would be able to not sleep during the day.

The third step is called “Considering options”. Now, the patient and the clinician try to ascertain what could be done to improve the current situation. Specifically, what can the patient do, what can the clinician do, what can others (such as a friend or other loved-one) do?

Example: The patient could be punctual with his taking of the medication and take them as they were prescribed, instead of taking them at uneven intervals. The patient could also refrain from lying in the bed during the day. This way he would have less of an incentive to sleep during the day. The clinician could revise and reduce the dosage of the medication, or change the regimen so that the sedating medication would be taken in the evening, before going to sleep. Patient’s friend could help by going out with him on regular walks in the afternoon, when the impulse to go to sleep is the strongest.

The fourth step is called “Agreeing on actions”. The clinician and the patient discuss and decide the specific actions that will be done in between the sessions. We underline once again that the patient should lead the discussion on actions, and all actions should be agreed upon by both parties (the clinician and the patient). Moreover, the actions are not an obligatory homework that the patient “must” perform. The clinician's approach here is to facilitate the improvement of the situation, and together with the patient, stimulate problem-solving skills. The actions should be formulated in a brief, clear manner, and should be precise, with a behavioural goal.

Example: All of the discussed actions during the previous step were specific and achievable, so the patient and the clinician agreed to enter them in the app. All of the described key components of DIALOG+ are illustrated in Figure x.

Ending the session and scheduling the next one

At this point, the clinician and the patient review the agreed actions once again. Patients should receive and keep with them the booklet that will include dates of your meetings, actions agreed after each session and any additional notes/reflections.

The patient can use this opportunity to write down the actions that he/she has planned to do, or the clinician can write them down for the patient. The session ends here, and the agreed actions and other data are stored in the app. At the beginning of the next session, the actions that were agreed upon during the previous session are displayed, so that the clinician and the patient can review what has been done in between the two sessions.

A2. ABOUT the IMPULSE STUDY

The IMPULSE study was conducted between 2018-2021, in Southeast European LMICs to evaluate the cost-effectiveness and implementation of the DIALOG+ for patients with PSD (Jovanovic et al, 2020; Jovanovic et al, 2021).

Figure A2. Key components of the IMPULSE study

Concisely, **the key components of the IMPULSE study** (Figure A2) included:

- (1) the analysis of the context for the delivery of DIALOG+
- (2) the development of an implementation strategy for the delivery of DIALOG+
- (3) performing a hybrid type II cluster RCT
- (4) upscaling and assessing sustainability of the intervention

The study started with **exploring the context** in which MH care is delivered to people with psychosis. To do this the interviews with patients, carers, MH staff and policy makers were conducted, and also policy documents and treatment guidelines were analysed.

Next, an **implementation strategy** was developed to make sure that the intervention (DIALOG+) can be successfully implemented in MH services. This included overcoming identified barriers such as limited time for clinicians (e.g. intervention can be delivered under 30 min), clinicians not feeling comfortable with using digital MH intervention (e.g. training included the use of computer tablets, and all clinicians were offered top up sessions and individual supervision), clinicians prejudice about working with paranoid patients (e.g. this was also tackled during training with case studies and specific examples).

The third step was to explore whether the intervention is effective and cost-saving for services in a **RCT**.

Who was included in the RCT?

Seventeen MH services were recruited whereby the goal was to include at least two services per country. A total of 81 clinicians (e.g. MH professionals with more than 6 months of experience working with patients with PSD in outpatient clinics) and 468 of their patients were enrolled. The sample consisted of adult outpatients of both genders (53% male, mean age 43 years), with a history of at least one hospital admission, with a primary diagnosis of psychosis or related disorder (60.7% schizophrenia, 14.3% bipolar disorder, 25.0% other diagnoses). Most of the patients did not receive any psychosocial treatment before their participation in this study (54.0%). Patients were excluded if having a diagnosis of organic brain disorders and if having severe cognitive deficits (unable to provide information to study instruments).

How was the RCT conducted?

Clinicians and their patients were randomized to deliver/receive either the DIALOG+ intervention (236 patients) or TAU that covered a brief assessment of MH and risks, medication side-effects, etc (232 patients). The intervention was delivered 6 times over 12 months, whereby the first three sessions were delivered monthly and the remaining sessions were delivered every three months. The main outcome measures were QoL, clinical symptoms, satisfaction with services and economic costs.

Finally, the last phase of the IMPULSE study was **to scale up the intervention and make it sustainable**. This means revising the implementation strategy and going back to stakeholders from the beginning of the story (patients, clinicians, policy makers, commissioners) to ensure the intervention is rolled out across services. The barriers to and reinforces of sustainability of this intervention have been explored separately.

A3. The Impulse Consortium

THE IMPULSE CONSORTIUM

Queen Mary University of London, United Kingdom (leading organisation)

Clinical Center of University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

University Clinic of Psychiatry – Skopje, North Macedonia

University of Pristina “Hasan Prishtina”, Kosovo* UN Resolution

Psychiatric Clinic in Podgorica, Montenegro

Faculty of Medicine, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia

CITY University of London, United Kingdom

User-led organisation Menssana, Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

User-led organisation Prostor, Belgrade, Serbia

References

- Bajs Janovic M, Bagaric A, Belavic A, Bilic V, Brecic P, Britvic D et al. (2020). In S Strkalj-Ivezic, M Kusan Jukic, D Stimac Grbic (Eds). *Mental health as public good – Psychosocial interventions in mental health*. Zagreb, Croatia: Croatian Institute of Public Health.
- Barth J, Munder T, Gerger H, Nuesch E, Trelle S, Znoj S et al. (2013). Comparative efficacy of seven psychotherapeutic interventions for patients with depression: a network meta-analysis. *PLoS Med*; 10(5):e1001454.
- Charlson F, Ferrari AJ, Santomauro DF, Dominic S, Stockings E, Scott JG et al. (2018). Global Epidemiology and Burden of Schizophrenia: Findings From the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016. *Schizophrenia Bulletin*; 44(6): 1195–1203.
- Cuijpers P, van Straten A, Smit F, Mihalopoulos C, Beekman A. (2008). Preventing the onset of depressive disorders: a meta-analytic review of psychological interventions. *Am J Psychiatry*; 165(10):1272–80.
- Cuijpers P, Sijbrandij M, Koole SL, Andersson G, Beekman AT, Reynolds 3rd CF. (2013). The efficacy of psychotherapy and pharmacotherapy in treating depressive and anxiety disorders: a meta-analysis of direct comparisons. *World Psychiatry*; 12(2):137–48.
- Cuijpers P, Sijbrandij M, Koole S, Huibers M, Berking M, Andersson G. (2014). Psychological treatment of generalized anxiety disorder: a meta-analysis. *Clin Psychol Rev*; 34(2):130–140.
- Dua T, Barbui C, Clark N, Fleischmann A, Poznyak V, van Ommeren et al. (2011). Evidence-based guidelines for mental, neurological, and substance use disorders in low- and middle-income countries: summary of WHO recommendations. *PLoS Med*; 8(11): e1001122.
- East London NHS Foundation Trust DIALOG+ Manual © 2020. Available at: <https://dialog.eft.nhs.uk/Resources>
- England MJ et al. Committee on Developing Evidence-Based Standards for Psychosocial Interventions for Mental Disorders; Board on Health Sciences Policy; Institute of Medicine. (2015). In MJ England, AS Butler and ML Gonzalez (Eds). *Psychosocial Interventions for Mental and Substance Use Disorders. A Framework for Establishing Evidence-Based Standards*. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US).
- Feng et al. (2021). Cost-effectiveness of implementing a digital psychosocial intervention for patients with psychotic spectrum disorders in low- and middle-income countries in South Eastern Europe: economic evaluation alongside a cluster randomised trial(unpublished data from the IMPULSE study).
- Fleischhacker WW, Keet IPM, Khan RS, EUFEST Steering Committee. (2005). The European First Episode Schizophrenia Trial (EUFEST): rationale and design of the trial. *Schizophr Res*; 78(2–3):147–56.

Institute of Medicine (US) Committee on Crossing the Quality Chasm: Adaptation to Mental Health and Addictive Disorders. (2006). *Improving the Quality of Health Care for Mental and Substance-Use Conditions: Quality Chasm Series*. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US).

Jovanovic N, Francis J, Maric NP, Arenliu A, Barjaktarov S, Dzibur Kulenovic A et al. (2020). Implementing a psychosocial intervention DIALOG+ for patients with psychotic disorders in low and middle income countries in South Eastern Europe: protocol for a hybrid effectiveness-implementation cluster randomized clinical trial (IMPULSE). *Global Psychiatry*; 3(1).

Jovanovic et al. (2021). Main RCT findings (unpublished data from the IMPULSE study).

Kilbourne AM, Beck K, Spaeth-Rublee B, Ramanuj P, O'Brien RW, Tomoyasi et al. Measuring and improving the quality of mental health care: a global perspective. *World psychiatry* 2018; 17(1): 30–8.

Lehman AF. (1988). A quality of life interview for the chronically mentally ill. *Evaluation and Program Planning*. 11(1): 51–62.

Maj M, van Os J, De Hert M, Gaebel W, Galderisi S, Green MF et al. (2021). The clinical characterization of the patient with primary psychosis aimed at personalization of management. *World Psychiatry*; 20(1): 4–33.

Maric NP, Andric Petrovic S, Rojnic-Kuzman M, Riecher-Rössler A. (2019). Implementation of early detection and intervention services for psychosis in Central and Eastern Europe: Current status. *Early Interv Psychiatry*; 13: 1283–1288.

McHugh RK, Whitton SW, Peckham AD, Welge JA, Otto MW. (2013). Patient Preference for Psychological vs. Pharmacological Treatment of Psychiatric Disorders: A Meta-Analytic Review. *J Clin Psychiatry*; 74(6): 595–602.

NICE guidelines: Psychosis and Schizophrenia in adults. (2014). Available from: <https://www.nice.org.uk/guidance/cg178/evidence/full-guideline-490503565> [Last accessed on 16 March 2021]

Pemovska et al. (2021). Process evaluation paper (unpublished data from the IMPULSE study).

Priebe S, Huxley P, Knight S, Evans S. (1999). Application and results of the Manchester Short Assessment of Quality of Life (MANSA). *Int J Soc Psychiatry*; 45(1): 7–12.

Priebe S, McCabe R. (2006). The therapeutic relationship in psychiatric settings. *Acta Psychiatr Scand-Suppl*; (429): 69–72.

Priebe S, McCabe R, Bullenkamp J, Hansson L, Lauber C, Martinez-Leal R et al. (2007). Structured patient–clinician communication and 1-year outcome in community mental healthcare: cluster randomised controlled trial. *Br J Psychiatry* ; 191(5): 420–426.

Priebe S, Kelley L, Golden E, McCrone P, Kingdon G, Rutterford C et al. (2013). Effectiveness of structured patient–clinician communication with a solution focused approach (DIALOG+) in community treatment of patients with psychosis – a cluster randomised controlled trial. *BMC Psychiatry*; 13: 173.

ISBN 978-1-910195-43-7

9 781910 195437